

Studies on Coordination Polymers of Fumaryl-bis-*N*-phenylhydroxamic Acid and Fumaryl-bis-*N*-*m*-tolylhydroxamic Acid with some Group III Elements

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Coordination polymers of fumaryl-bis-*N*-phenylhydroxamic acid (FPHA) and fumarvl-bis-*N*-*m*-tolylhydroxamic acid (FTHA) with some group III metals were synthesised. These coordination polymers have been characterised by their elemental analysis, IR and reflectance spectral data, conductance and DTA measurements.

THE survey of literature available on coordination polymers shows that most of the work which is synthetic in nature centres around the transition metal ions. These metals have been used with their oxidation number two with different bis-ligands. The simultaneous fulfilment of the coordination number as well as the oxidation number resulted into neutral highly insoluble co-ordination polymers. The work on group III elements, particularly with oxidation number three, has not been attempted in detail as a simple bis-ligand is not able to yield the polymers of desired nature. In such cases, however, the use of primary comparatively less stable complex is made and ultimately the product is a mixed ligand coordination polymer or complex.

Coordination polymers of a number of bis-hydroxamic acids with transition metals have been reported by Kharche¹. However, coordination polymers of bis-hydroxamic acids with group III elements are rarely studied. Fumaryl-bis-*N*-phenyl- and fumaryl-bis-*N*-*m*-tolyl-hydroxamic acids have been synthesised for the first time in these laboratories². Present investigation includes synthesis and characterisation of coordination polymers of FPFA and FTHA.

Experimental

The chemicals used were all of AnalaR or chemically pure grade.

Preparation of ligands : The general methods employed in the synthesis of *N*-arylhydroxamic acids are outlined in the literature^{3,4}. Freshly prepared *N*-arylhydroxylamine and vacuum-distilled acid chloride in stoichiometric proportions were reacted at low temperatures (0° or lower). Dicarboxic acid (i.e. fumaric acid) was used for the synthesis of FPFA and FTHA. Firstly, the acid dichloride was prepared and then it was condensed with two moles of *N*-phenylhydroxylamine and *N*-*m*-tolylhydroxylamine separately which were obtained by controlled reduction of nitrobenzene and *m*-nitrotoluene.

bis-hydroxamic acid

where, R = C₆H₅ or CH₃.C₆H₄.

Synthesis of coordination polymers : Coordination polymers were prepared by the reaction of metal acetylacetonates/metal oxinates and bis-ligands employing suitable solvent medium under proper set of conditions; which includes first the preparation of primary complexes either β-diketonates or oxinates.

Preparation of simple complexes or primary complexes : Methods previously employed^{5,6} for the preparation of β-diketonates involve the addition of sodium or ammonium β-diketone to the metal salt solution. In the case of oxinates, 8-hydroxyquinoline dissolved in dilute acetic acid was added to the metal salt solution and pH was adjusted with dilute ammonia.

Preparation of mixed ligand coordination polymers : Coordination polymers of FPFA and FTFA with group III metals were prepared by heating and then digesting the mixture containing ligand (0.005 mol) and metal acetylacetonates (0.005 mol) or metal oxinates (0.005 mol) on water-bath. Table 1 shows different solvent ratios that were

spectra (400-4 000 cm^{-1}) were obtained using a Specord-75 spectrophotometer in nujol. A single beam Karl-Zeiss VSU-2-p spectrophotometer was used for recording reflectance spectra. A Beltronix million megohm meter MM 500 (India) was used to measure the conductance. Magnetic susceptibility was determined by Gouy's method¹.

TABLE 1—PREPARATIVE CONDITIONS OF POLYMERS OF FPFA AND FTFA WITH GROUP III METAL IONS

Polymer	Solvent DMF-EtOH ratio (v/v)	Remarks
Al ^{III} -acac-FPFA	1 : 4	Amorphous
Al ^{III} -oxine-FPFA	2 : 3	Amorphous
Sc ^{III} -acac-FPFA	2 : 3	Crystalline
Y ^{III} -acac-FPFA	3 : 2	Crystalline
La ^{III} -acac-FPFA	4 : 1	Crystalline
Al ^{III} -acac-FTFA	1 : 4	Amorphous
Sc ^{III} -acac-FTFA	2 : 3	Crystalline
Y ^{III} -acac-FTFA	3 : 2	Crystalline
La ^{III} -acac-FTFA	4 : 1	Amorphous

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of polymers (Table 2) suggest general formula (M-acac-FPFA)_n, (M-oxine-FPFA)_n and (M-acac-FTFA)_n. Most of these polymers were found to contain some water molecules as water of crystallisation.

The ir spectra of a number of coordination polymers of bis-hydroxamic acids have been investigated and reported by Kharche¹ and Gandhi². Ir spectra of FPFA and FTFA show the presence of OH stretching band around 3 100 cm^{-1} (OH) which disappears in polymers indicating coordination to the central metal ion *via* deprotonation. The three

TABLE 2—CHARACTERISATION DATA OF COORDINATION POLYMERS OF FPFA AND FTFA WITH GROUP III METAL IONS

Sl. no.	Polymer (assigned composition)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Decomp. temp. °C	Specific resistance $\Omega \text{ cm}$
		C	H	N	M		
(a) FPFA (L) polymers :							
1.	{[Al-L-acac].3H ₂ O} _n	53.10 (52.85)	4.95 (5.25)	6.10 (5.88)	6.30 (5.65)	410	7.0 × 10 ⁷
2.	{[Al-L-oxine].3H ₂ O} _n	56.45 (57.59)	4.78 (4.60)	7.31 (8.06)	6.02 (5.16)	355	1.0 × 10 ⁸
3.	{[Sc-L-acac].H ₂ O} _n	56.30 (55.03)	4.62 (4.58)	6.95 (6.11)	8.75 (9.81)	320	8.8 × 10 ⁷
4.	{[Y-L-acac].3H ₂ O} _n	43.20 (42.43)	4.69 (4.64)	6.17 (5.20)	15.98 (16.50)	300	9.1 × 10 ⁷
5.	{[La-L-acac].3H ₂ O} _n	41.30 (42.76)	3.95 (4.25)	5.02 (4.76)	24.90 (23.6)	295	4.4 × 10 ⁸
(b) FTFA (L') polymers :							
1.	{[Al-L'-acac].2H ₂ O} _n	57.70 (56.86)	5.13 (5.55)	5.01 (5.76)	4.82 (5.53)	305	1.1 × 10 ⁸
2.	[Sc-L'-acac] _n	58.60 (58.19)	5.32 (4.91)	6.12 (5.98)	8.60 (9.59)	285	4.1 × 10 ⁷
3.	{[Y-L'-acac].3H ₂ O} _n	47.60 (48.77)	4.76 (5.12)	4.41 (4.94)	16.90 (15.7)	326	6.3 × 10 ⁷
4.	{[La-L'-acac].3H ₂ O} _n	42.91 (44.81)	4.16 (4.70)	4.14 (4.54)	25.00 (26.90)	270	4.9 × 10 ⁸

taken. For a series, the conditions were same but to increase the yield and to overcome the solubility difficulties of the reactants, different ratios of the solvents were taken. All the polymers were bright-yellow in colour and insoluble in all common organic solvents. Hence, the products were purified by repeated washings with the solvents employed for their preparation.

Physical measurements : The D.T.A. apparatus fabricated at I.I.T., Bombay was used for recording thermograms of the compounds in air. The infrared

consecutive bands 1 625, 1 600 and 1 570 cm^{-1} of FPFA and 1 650, 1 630 and 1 600 cm^{-1} of FTFA which exist due to various resonating structures of R-N(C=O)-OH in these ligands, shifted towards lower frequency side in these polymers indicating the coordination through carbonyl group forming a C=O . M linkage.

The N-O stretching vibrations are found at 965 and 950 cm^{-1} in FPFA and FTFA. This particular band is reported to be shifted towards higher frequency side with an increase in intensity⁷. However, in the polymers of hydroxamic acids with

TABLE 3—INFRARED SPECTRAL BONDS* (CM⁻¹) OF FPFA AND FTHA POLYMERS WITH GROUP III METAL IONS

(a) FPFA polymers :

FPFA	acac	oxine	Al ^{III} -acac	Al ^{III} -oxine	Sc ^{III} -acac	Y ^{III} -acac	La ^{III} -acac	Assignments
—	—	—	3 200- 3 500 b	3 200- 3 500 b	3 200- 3 500 b	3 200- 3 500 b	3 200- 3 500 b	II-O-II
3 100 mb	—	3 300- 3 500 b	—	—	—	—	—	OH of oxine and FPFA C=N of oxine C=O of FPFA and acetylacetonc
—	—	1 577	—	1 575 sh	—	—	—	
1 640 sh	—	—	1 660 sm	1 660 sh	1 650 s	1 650 sm	1 650 sh	
1 625 sh	1 709	—	1 620 sm	1 560 sh	1 560 sh	1 600 sh	1 560 sh	
1 600 sh	—	—	1 580 sm	—	—	—	—	
1 570 sh	—	—	1 540 sh	1 540 sm	1 530 sm	1 530 sh	1 540 s	C-O of oxine at C-O ..M site N-O stretch of FPFA
—	—	—	—	1 105 sm	—	—	—	
965 s	—	—	950 sm	950 sm	950 sm	950 sm	950 sm	

(b) FTHA polymers :

FTHA	acac	Al ^{III} -acac	Sc ^{III} -acac	Y ^{III} -acac	La ^{III} -acac	Assignments
—	—	3 200- 3 500 b	—	3 200- 3 500 b	3 200- 3 500 b	H-O-H
3 100 b	—	—	—	—	—	OH of FTHA C=O of FTHA and acetylacetonc
1 650 sh	—	1 650 sh	1 650 sh	1 650 s	1 650 sh	
1 630 sm	1 709	1 590 sm	1 590 sh	1 590 s	1 575 sh	
1 600 sh	—	1 525 sm	1 520 sm	1 520 b	1 530 b	
950 s	—	950 sm	950 sm	950 sm	950 sm	N-O stretch of FTHA

*b ≡ broad, sh ≡ shoulder, sm ≡ strong medium, s ≡ strong, m ≡ medium.

several transition metal ions prepared in these laboratories the shifting of this band is found towards lower frequency side as well as higher frequency side. This band is shifted towards lower frequency side in FPFA polymers and there is no change in its position in FTHA polymers.

The presence of band at 3 500-3 400 cm⁻¹ indicates lattice water in these polymers except in the case of Sc^{III}-acac-FTHA. In the case of polymers prepared using metal acetylacetonate combination, the C=O stretch of treacetylacetonc at 1 707 cm⁻¹ is shifted towards lower frequency side and appeared in the region 1 650-1 575 cm⁻¹ suggesting coordination of acetylacetonc also to the central metal ion. In the same way, the coordination of oxine to the central metal ion is shown by the shifting of 1 577 cm⁻¹ of C=N stretch to 1 575 cm⁻¹ and another band around 1 100 cm⁻¹ due to C-O stretch at C-O ..M site (Table 3).

The study of reflectance spectra showed that the maximum absorbance is at 350 nm for both the ligands. Polymers showed an absorption maxima in the region 370 to 420 nm and the complexation shift is towards higher frequency side. The spectra obtained are due to charge transfer.

Magnetic moments of FPFA and FTHA polymers showed that all the polymers are diamagnetic.

Thermal studies of coordination polymers of bis-hydroxamic acids have been reported¹. All these polymers show a sharp exotherm besides the larger one at temperatures range 125-300°. It has been

observed in case of few polymers that the small exothermic peak is not associated with weight loss. This is reported as due to solid-solid phase transition, probably a structural change occurring after the removal of water of crystallisation or otherwise⁸.

On the basis of above grounds D.T.A. of FPFA and FTHA polymers have been studied. These polymers are of the same nature as discussed above and the only difference is the presence of a primary ligand and its contribution towards the heat stability. Decomposition temperatures are reported on the basis of D.T.A. (Table 2). The second exothermic peak being very large, the temperature corresponding to its starting point is taken as the decomposition temperature. A sharp exothermic peak (160-300°) is followed by the larger one (270-410°) in these compounds, and the larger one is associated with the major weight loss. As the TGA is not carried out for these polymers, a detailed discussion is not possible.

From decomposition temperatures supported by specific resistance date for FPFA and FTHA polymers it has been found that in the case of Al^{III}-, Sc^{III}-, Y^{III}- and La^{III}-acac-FPFA polymers, thermal stability decreases from Al^{III} to La^{III}. In the case of FTHA polymers Al^{III}, Sc^{III}, Y^{III}, and La^{III}, thermal stability decreases from Al^{III} to La^{III}. However, Y^{III}-acac-FTHA polymer is thermally more stable than Sc^{III}-acac-FTHA polymer which may be due to difference in the degree of polymerisation. Of all the polymers, Al^{III}-acac-FPFA polymer has the highest heat stability.

TABLE 4—PROPOSED STRUCTURE OF THE POLYMERIC UNIT

Metal-acac-FPHA ($R = C_6H_5$)

Metal-acac-FTHA ($R = CH_2C_6H_4$)

$M = Al^{III}, Sc^{III}, Y^{III}, La^{III}$

Metal-oxine-FPHA ($R = C_6H_5$)

$M = Al^{III}$

The specific resistance of FPHA and FTHA polymers are given in Table 2.

Proposed structures: The confirmation and characterisation of the compounds prepared in the present course of investigations are no doubt difficult because of their insolubility and intractibility. Their formation as polymers from steric considerations and establishing the structures on the basis of elemental analysis are therefore tentative (Table 4).

The composition has been suggested on the basis of elemental analysis (Table 2) which is also explained by ir spectra. Observations of the composition of some of the compounds lead to the conclusion that they should be simple polynuclear complexes,

but their extreme insolubility makes one to believe in their polymeric nature with more complex features present

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